
Study on the Influence Law of Admixtures on the Mechanical Properties of Self-Healing Sealing Materials

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Abstract: As the depth of coal mining in China increases, the threat of gas disasters intensifies. Pre-drainage of coal-bed methane is a key measure to prevent such disasters, and the quality of borehole sealing directly determines gas-extraction efficiency. Traditional cement-based sealing materials, however, readily lose water, shrink and crack, and leak easily under ground stress, leading to poor extraction performance. Therefore, a regenerative self-healing sealing material was developed. It can automatically repair cracks that form at grouting points, but the incorporated healing agents retard cement hydration and reduce the mechanical strength of the seal. To mitigate this adverse effect, the self-healing sealing material was modified so that it retains its self-healing capacity while improving mechanical performance. Mechanical tests showed that the modified material possesses much better properties than the unmodified version: its compressive strength reached 8.43 MPa, approximately three times that of the control group. SEM-EDS and XRF comparative analyses of the two sealing materials revealed that the modified self-healing seal has a denser micro-structure and higher mass fractions of Ca and Si. XRD comparative analysis indicated a reduction in unhydrated cement phases, faster hydration, and the formation of new silicate and calcium phases. The results demonstrate that the modified self-healing sealing material hydrates more rapidly and its mechanical performance is markedly improved.

Keywords: Coal-bed methane drainage; self-healing sealing material; nano-SiO₂; mechanical properties

1. Introduction

With the increase in coal mining depth in China, geological conditions have become increasingly complex, and the threat of gas disasters has grown more severe. Pre-extraction of coal seam gas is a fundamental measure to prevent gas disasters [1], and its effectiveness is directly influenced by the quality of borehole sealing. Currently, the most widely used sealing material is cement-based, but traditional cement materials are prone to water loss and shrinkage and tend to crack under in-situ stress, creating gas leakage channels that ultimately lead to poor gas extraction efficiency [2]. To address this issue, the research team has proposed developing self-healing sealing materials for re-generated fractures: when re-generated fractures occur at the grouted sealing section, the material can undergo a precipitation reaction with the leaking air to form a healing product, which re-seals the fractures and improves extraction efficiency [3]. However, the incorporation of self-healing agents affects the mechanical properties of the sealing material, so it is necessary to modify the self-healing sealing material to enhance its mechanical properties and ensure it meets the requirements for borehole sealing [4].

In terms of improving the mechanical properties of cement-based materials, many scholars have conducted relevant research. Wang Zhixin [5] studied the effects of single incorporation of vinyl acetate-ethylene (VAE) copolymer latex powder or composite incorporation of VAE latex powder and nano-silicon dioxide (NS) on the mechanical properties and crack resistance of cement-based materials. It was found that the composite incorporation of VAE/NS reduced the content of Ca(OH)₂, further enhanced the bonding between hydration products, decreased the calcium-silicon ratio of hydration products, and optimized the microstructure of the material, thereby improving the mechanical properties and crack resistance of cement-based materials. Yu

Baoying [6] et al. investigated the influence of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fiber length on the early mechanical properties of cement matrix. They found that under the same dosage, the longer the fiber length, the better the mechanical properties of the cement matrix, and the incorporation of fibers made the microstructure of the cement matrix more compact. Zhang Songlei [7] et al. studied the effect of graphene oxide (GO for short) on the strength of desert sand cement-based materials through orthogonal experiments and found that GO could optimize the microstructural morphology of cement hydration products and produce a positive correlation effect with the active materials in desert sand. Hassan et al. [8, 9] studied the impact of mineral admixtures on the properties of low-strength concrete and found that composite incorporation of mineral additives could effectively improve the mechanical properties of low-strength concrete. Moreover, with the extension of curing age, the mechanical properties of the specimens measured after 90 days were significantly stronger than those measured at 28 days. Mohammed et al. [10] researched the effect of nano-silicon dioxide on the properties of pervious concrete and found that the incorporation of nano-silicon dioxide could improve the compressive strength of pervious concrete without adverse effects on the porosity and permeability of the concrete. Moradpour et al. [11] studied the influence of nano-magnesium oxide on the permeability of cement mortar, and found that the hydration products of nano-magnesium oxide could increase the density of cement mortar, thereby improving the mechanical strength of cement mortar.

Experiments have shown that the incorporation of self-healing agents reduces the mechanical properties of cement-based composites [12], and there are mainly two possible reasons for this reduction: first, the bonding strength between the crystals formed by the reaction of self-healing agents and cement hydration products is relatively low, and the surface of cement particles is adsorbed by the self-healing agents, which makes ion exchange at the solid-liquid interface difficult and slows down the cement hydration rate [13]; second, the main components of self-healing agents contain a large number of carboxyl groups, endowing them with strong adsorption and complexation capabilities, so adsorption and complexation reactions occur when mixed with cement [14], and the adsorption effect hinders the dissolution of cement mineral phases, poisons the nucleation sites of calcium silicate hydrate (C—S—H), and inhibits the nucleation and growth of calcium-containing hydration products [15].

In this study, nano-silicon dioxide was used to modify the self-healing sealing material. The changes in mechanical properties of the self-healing sealing material before and after modification were investigated, and SEM-EDS, XRF, and XRD experiments were conducted to compare the micro-morphology, element distribution, and phase composition of the two sealing materials. The reasons for the changes in mechanical properties of the two sealing materials were analyzed from a microscopic perspective, laying a theoretical foundation for efficient borehole sealing in gas extraction.

2. Experimental Overview

Experimental Materials and Proportions

In the experiment, ordinary Portland cement of Grade 42.5 was selected, which is specifically composed of cement clinker, admixtures, and desulfurized gypsum. Other chemical reagents besides Portland cement include: self-healing agent YA, crystallizing agent A, alkali activators I and II, calcium silicate, and nano-silica (with a particle size of 50 nm). The mix ratio schemes of the two self-healing sealing materials (before and after modification) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Self-healing sealing material mix ratio

	self-healing agent YA	crystallizing agent	alkali activator I	alkali activator II	nano-silica	calcium silicate	cement
before modification	20%	10%	10%			10%	50%
after modification	10%	3.3%	4.9%	1.7%	1.5%		78.6%

Test Sample Preparation

In accordance with the experimental protocol, accurately weigh cement, various admixtures, and other required raw materials to ensure the accuracy and precision of weighing. After blending the admixtures with Portland cement in accordance with the mix ratios specified in Table 1, add tap water for mixing. Pay attention to

controlling conditions such as mixing time, mixing speed, ambient temperature, and humidity to ensure the consistency and quality of the test specimens. Once fully mixed, pour the mixture into standard molds of $\phi 50\text{mm} \times 100\text{mm}$, level the surface, cover the surface of the slurry with plastic wrap, and place the samples under standard air conditions for curing. After the samples have completely set, demold them for subsequent experiments such as crack self-healing tests and mechanical strength tests.

Crack Self-Healing Experiment

After demolding, the samples were cured for 7 days. Subsequently, a hydraulic press (Figure 1) was used to completely split the specimens via the Brazilian splitting method. Thereafter, the splitting specimens were bound and spliced using nylon cable ties, with a gap of approximately 1 mm reserved at the splicing joint. The spliced specimens were then placed back under air environmental conditions for curing. Meanwhile, a high-definition measuring microscope (Figure 2) was employed to conduct regular observations and record the changes in the crack width of different samples.

Figure 1: Hydraulic press

Figure 2: High-definition measuring microscope

Mechanical Properties Testing Experiment

To obtain the uniaxial compressive strength of the self-healing plugging materials before and after modification, a compressive test was conducted on the plugging materials. The test samples were standard mold specimens ($\phi 50\text{mm} \times 100\text{mm}$) of four types of self-healing plugging materials (both unmodified and modified). The test instrument used was a 5000 kN computer-controlled electro-hydraulic servo universal testing machine. The computer-controlled electro-hydraulic servo universal testing machine is a high-precision equipment applied in the field of material mechanical property testing. It is mainly used to test the mechanical property parameters of materials such as tensile strength, compressive strength, and bending strength under static or dynamic loading conditions, so as to evaluate the mechanical properties of the materials. Figure 3 shows the 5000 kN computer-controlled electro-hydraulic servo universal testing machine used in the compressive test of this study.

Figure 3: Microcomputer-controlled electro-hydraulic universal testing machine

The experiment was conducted using a displacement-controlled loading method, with a loading displacement rate of 2 kN/min. After setting the parameters, the samples were placed in the designated area for the experiment (Figure 2-12). Upon completion of the experiment, the acquired data were processed to obtain the corresponding stress-strain curves and analyze the relevant key mechanical characteristics. The data obtained from the experiment included the load applied to the specimens under pressure and the corresponding indenter displacement. These data needed to be calculated using Formulas (2-1 and 2-2) to convert them into the corresponding stress and strain, where the compressive strength is the peak stress.

$$R_c = \frac{F_c}{A} \quad (0.1)$$

In the formula, R_c denotes the stress exerted on the specimen, F_c represents the load force applied to the specimen, and A stands for the compressed area of the specimen.

$$S_c = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0} \quad (0.2)$$

In the formula, S_c denotes the strain of the specimen, ΔL represents the deformation of the specimen, and L_0 stands for the original dimension of the specimen.

SEM-EDS Experiment

The experimental samples were powder samples of two types of self-healing plugging materials (unmodified and modified), and the powder samples were required to pass through a 200-mesh sieve. A Regulus 8100 ultra-high-resolution cold-field emission scanning electron microscope was used as the experimental instrument, with the accelerating voltage set to 5 kV. The microscopic morphology of the samples was observed, and an X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) was used to analyze the types and contents of elements in the regions with special microscopic morphology of the samples.

XRF Experiment

The experimental instrument used is a Shimadzu XRF-1800 wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer. It is employed for qualitative and semi-quantitative analysis of the hydration products of self-healing sealing materials.

XRD Experiment

The experimental samples were powder samples of two types of self-healing plugging materials (unmodified and modified). A D8 Advance polycrystalline (powder) X-ray diffractometer manufactured by Bruker Corporation (Germany) was used as the experimental instrument, with the tested 2θ angle range set between 5° and 90° . The XRD patterns of the two samples were subjected to phase identification and analysis.

3. Analysis of Experimental Results

Evaluation of Crack Self-Healing Potential

Figure 4 shows the formation of self-healing products of the self-healing sealing materials (before and after modification) when placed in air. The unmodified sealing material starts to form precipitated products as early as 1 day after being placed in air, while the modified one begins to generate such precipitates around day 7. Although the rate of precipitate formation slows down, the quantity of precipitates produced is still sufficient to meet the repair requirements.

Figure 4: Self-healing product formation law

Figure 5 presents the crack self-healing status of the self-healing sealing material after 7 days of curing in air. As can be observed from the figure, the maximum initial widths of the cracks in the two groups are 0.95 mm and 0.63 mm, respectively. After 1 day of healing, the maximum remaining width of the crack in the unmodified self-healing sealing material is 0.31 mm, while that in the modified one is 0.24 mm. The cracks are basically healed after 3 days of healing, and completely closed at the crack sites after 5 days, with a tighter bonding effect.

Figure 5: Crack self-healing situation

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that under air conditions, the crack self-healing rate of the control group is the fastest. This indicates that the added self-healing agent delays the hydration of cement, leaving more unhydrated cement available for reacting to form crack-healing products—and this is also the reason for its relatively poor mechanical properties. For the three modified self-healing sealing materials, the introduction of nano-silica not only reduces the dosage of the self-healing agent but also increases the proportion of cement. Although their crack self-healing rate is lower than that of the unmodified material, they can still completely heal cracks of approximately 0.7 mm after 5 days of healing.

Analysis of Experimental Results for Mechanical Property Testing

Figure 6 shows the stress-strain curves of the self-healing sealing material before and after modification. As can be seen from the figure, there are differences in the stress-strain curves between the two groups of self-healing sealing materials with different mix ratios. Among them, the stress of the unmodified self-healing sealing

material increases slowly, and its peak stress is significantly lower than that of the modified one, reaching only 2.87 MPa. It has a short elastic stage, showing a low elastic modulus (i.e., low stiffness) and weak overall strength. For the modified self-healing sealing material, the peak stress reaches 8.43 MPa, demonstrating the optimal compressive strength performance. It has the longest elastic stage and the highest stiffness, thus exhibiting the strongest ability to withstand deformation in the initial stage. Additionally, the plastic stage shows a slow decline, reflecting good ductility. Compared with the unmodified material, its compressive strength has increased by approximately 3 times, indicating a significant improvement in mechanical properties.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curve

The latter (referring to the modified material) has significantly improved the compressive strength and elastic modulus of the material through nano-silica modification, while also enhancing its plastic deformation capacity. The addition of nano-silica improves the material's microstructure, thereby boosting its mechanical properties. Among the groups, the final optimized group exhibits the highest compressive strength. In summary, the mix ratio of the optimized group achieves a comprehensive enhancement of mechanical properties, which meets the basic requirements for sealing applications.

Analysis of SEM-EDS Experimental Results

Figure 7 shows the SEM microtopography of hydration products of the two self-healing sealing materials (before and after modification). As can be seen from the figure, the cement hydration products of the control group exhibit diverse morphologies, including irregular flake-like, flocculent, and honeycomb-like structures. These structures are relatively disordered, with numerous gaps and cracks, and a large number of pores with significant size differences—ranging from small micropores to large holes. This structure leads to inconsistent mechanical properties of the material in different directions. The larger cracks become areas of stress concentration, which reduces the overall mechanical strength of the material and results in poor compactness. The hydration products fail to fully fill the cement matrix, leaving many loose areas. This is unfavorable for withstanding large external forces, especially in terms of poor compressive performance.

In the microtopography of the hydration products of the optimized group, relatively slender fibrous structures are observed. These fibers are intertwined with each other to form a network structure. Generally, such fibrous structures are calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gels, which can fill the micro-pores in the cement-based material, increase the material's compactness and strength, and improve its mechanical properties and durability. The optimized group has the lowest porosity, and its C-S-H gel develops most fully, presenting an interwoven fibrous structure with a highly dense microstructure. This dense microstructure and sufficient production of hydration products enable the material to reach the highest level of mechanical properties. There are very few pores, and the existing ones are small. The hydration products show a high degree of crystallization, with flake-like and fibrous structures closely connected to form a solid integral structure. This structure can effectively transfer and disperse stress, preventing the cement from cracking easily under compression and thus giving it high compressive strength.

Figure 7: Microscopic morphology of hydration products

The EDS spectrum results of the hydration products of the two self-healing sealing materials (before and after modification) are shown in Figure 8. As can be seen from Figure 8, the elements in the hydration products of both groups of self-healing sealing materials are mainly O, C, Ca, and Si, but there are significant differences in the content of each element. Among them, the control group has the lowest contents of Ca and Si elements, which significantly reduces the production of C-S-H gel. The excessively high content of C element is due to the incomplete reaction of a large amount of carbonaceous substances or excessive carbonation, which significantly affects the mechanical properties of the sealing material and leads to poor overall mechanical properties of the material. In addition, the extremely low content of Al element results in insufficient formation of ettringite (AFt), further weakening its early strength. For the optimized group, the relatively high content of Ca element is conducive to the formation of the hydration product C-S-H gel, while the increased content of Si element further promotes the production of C-S-H gel, enhancing the comprehensive strength of the cement. The content of C element is moderate, which has a slight impact on the strength of the cement but causes little interference. The relatively high content of Al element helps to form ettringite (AFt), thereby enhancing the early strength.

Figure 8: Microscopic element analysis of hydration products

Analysis of XRF Experimental Results

The fluorescent X-ray intensity of each element in the hydration product sample of the self-healing sealing material is correlated with the content of that element in the sample. Based on this, quantitative analysis of the elements in the crack self-healing product samples of the self-healing sealing material was conducted through XRF experiments. The semi-quantitative analysis results of each element in the crack self-healing products obtained in the experiment are presented in the form of corresponding oxides, as shown in Table 2. It can be seen from Table 4-1 that the hydration products of the self-healing sealing material (both before and after modification) have the highest mass fractions of compounds such as Na₂O, Al₂O₃, SiO₂, and CaO, but there are significant differences in their specific contents.

Table 2: Semi - quantitative analysis results of elements in hydration products.

Group element	before modification	after modification
Na ₂ O	17.1	10.2
MgO	1.54	1.67
Al ₂ O ₃	3.82	3.98
SiO ₂	22.8	21.7
P ₂ O ₅	0.0856	0.126
SO ₃	0.990	1.58
Cl	0.0745	0.0710
K ₂ O	0.763	1.18
CaO	49.6	56.5
TiO ₂	0.413	0.442
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.54	2.69
ZnO	0.0569	0.0652
SrO	0.176	0.199

Among the two groups of samples, CaO has the highest content, accounting for 49.6% and 56.5% respectively. This indicates that the content of Ca element is the highest, and Ca²⁺ compounds are one of the main components of cement hydration products. The variation in their content is mainly due to the change in cement content in the mix ratio. The content of Na element shows a significant variation. This is because the admixture added in the control group contains a relatively large amount of Na⁺ compounds. An appropriate amount of Na⁺ can accelerate the hydration process and improve the pore structure; however, an excessive Na⁺ content will cause the sealing material to expand and crack, thereby reducing its compressive strength and durability. In contrast, the Na⁺ content in the modified self-healing sealing material is significantly lower than that in the unmodified one, which contributes to the improved mechanical strength of the optimized group. Si element is mainly derived from C-S-H (calcium silicate hydrate), a key contributor to cement strength. A relatively high Si content usually indicates a greater production of C-S-H, leading to a denser cementitious system and higher mechanical strength. Nevertheless, the high Si content in the unmodified sample is attributed to the added calcium silicate. However, the incorporation of the self-healing agent delays cement hydration, resulting in lower mechanical strength. In the modified material, the relatively high Si content is due to the added nano-silica. With high reactivity, nano-silica can undergo a secondary reaction with calcium hydroxide (CH) (a product of cement hydration) to generate more calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H). The increased C-S-H gel can further fill pores, enhancing the mechanical strength of the sealing material. As for Al element, it participates in the formation of calcium aluminate hydration products in cement, which plays an important role in the early strength development. However, the Al content remains relatively stable in both groups, exerting little influence on the variation of mechanical strength.

Analysis of XRD Experimental Results

Figure 9 shows the XRD patterns of the hydration products of the two self-healing sealing materials (before and after modification). As can be seen from the figure, the control group has relatively high contents of C₃S (tricalcium silicate) and C₂S (dicalcium silicate), along with a large amount of unreacted SiO₂ (silicon dioxide)

and Al_2O_3 (aluminum oxide), as well as a high content of complex calcium silicate carbonate—all of which lead to its low strength.

For the optimized group, the content of C_3S is relatively reduced, and the content of calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) also decreases to some extent. This is due to the addition of nano-silica, which triggers a pozzolanic reaction between calcium hydroxide and nano-silica, generating more C-S-H (calcium silicate hydrate) gel. This indicates that the hydration of the optimized group is more sufficient, resulting in the highest early strength; meanwhile, the appropriate proportion of C_2S ensures the growth of late-stage strength.

New hydration products appear in the optimized group, including calcite (CaCO_3), tilleyite ($\text{Ca}_5\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7(\text{CO}_3)_2$), and aluminosilicate (Al_2SiO_5). Among them, tilleyite and aluminosilicate are newly formed silicates, which are hydration products of tricalcium silicate, dicalcium silicate, and other components—indicating that the modified sealing material accelerates the cement hydration process. The formation of calcite also helps to make its internal structure more compact.

Figure 9: XRD of hydration products

4. Mechanism of the Effect of Admixtures on the Mechanical Properties of Self-Healing Sealing Materials Mechanism of the Effect of Repair Agents on the Mechanical Properties of Self-Healing Sealing Materials

Based on the previous experimental results, it can be concluded that the addition of self-healing agents delays the hydration process of Portland cement, thereby reducing the mechanical properties of the sealing materials. Since the crack repair products can only form in the presence of unhydrated cement, the self-healing sealing materials contain a relatively large amount of unhydrated cement, which undergoes a secondary hydration reaction to facilitate the repair process. Secondly, according to the previous SEM-EDS experimental results, the addition of self-healing agents leads to an increase in the pore size of the sealing materials and a higher porosity, resulting in a relatively loose microstructure. This loose structure, in turn, causes excessive carbonation of the sealing materials.

Mechanism of the Effect of Nano-SiO₂ on the Mechanical Properties of Self-Healing Sealing Materials

Through analysis and summary, the mechanism of the effect of Nano-SiO₂ on the mechanical properties of self-healing sealing materials is illustrated in Figure 4-6. The influence of Nano-SiO₂ on the mechanical properties of self-healing sealing materials is mainly achieved through its unique nano-scale characteristics, high specific surface area, and chemical activity. These properties enable Nano-SiO₂ to play multiple roles during the hydration process of self-healing sealing materials, thereby significantly improving the microstructure and mechanical properties of the materials. The addition of Nano-SiO₂ can promote the hydration reaction of cement, accelerate the formation of hydration products, and enhance the early strength of the materials. Meanwhile, Nano-SiO₂ can fill the tiny pores in the cement matrix, reduce porosity, optimize the microstructure, and make the materials more dense and uniform. In addition, Nano-SiO₂ can also undergo a pozzolanic reaction with calcium hydroxide (a hydration product of cement) to generate more calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) gel, which further improves the compactness and strength of the materials. These mechanisms work together to significantly enhance the mechanical property indicators of self-healing sealing materials, such as compressive strength, flexural strength, and elastic modulus. This allows the materials to meet the high-strength requirements in practical applications while maintaining their self-healing capability.

(1) Filling Effect

The particle size of Nano-SiO₂ particles is typically much smaller than that of cement particles. These nanoparticles can penetrate into the tiny pores of the sealing materials, reduce the porosity, minimize the penetration paths of water and harmful substances, and thereby improve the impermeability and erosion resistance of the sealing materials. By filling the pores, Nano-SiO₂ makes the microstructure of the sealing materials denser, which in turn enhances their mechanical strength and durability. Nano-SiO₂ particles have high surface energy, enabling them to undergo physical adsorption in the sealing materials and form a tight bond with cement hydration products. The combined effect of physical adsorption and filling effect of Nano-SiO₂ strengthens the internal structure of the sealing materials. Physical adsorption creates a strong interaction between Nano-SiO₂ particles and cement hydration products, improving the integrity and stability of the materials. The filling effect further eliminates weak points in the sealing materials, allowing stress to be transmitted more uniformly without easily causing stress concentration. This synergistic effect enables the sealing materials to exhibit higher strength and better deformation resistance when subjected to external forces, significantly enhancing their mechanical properties.

(2) Accelerating Hydration Reaction

Nano-SiO₂ exhibits high chemical activity, which enables it to accelerate the hydration reaction of cement. This acceleration promotes the formation of more hydration products (e.g., calcium silicate hydrate, C-S-H) in a short period, thereby enhancing the early strength of the cement. Nano-SiO₂ can also facilitate the dissolution of silicate minerals (e.g., tricalcium silicate, C₃S), leading to the generation of additional C-S-H gel and a subsequent improvement in early strength. During the cement hydration process, the incorporation of Nano-SiO₂ further promotes the formation of C-S-H gel. As the primary hydration product of cement-based materials, the quantity and structure of C-S-H gel have a significant impact on the mechanical properties of cement paste. The addition of Nano-SiO₂ increases the yield of C-S-H gel, which in turn fills the pores in the sealing material and improves its compactness. This enhanced compactness helps strengthen the mechanical properties of the sealing material, allowing it to better withstand external forces under loading, while reducing stress concentration and crack propagation.

(3) Pozzolanic Reaction

Nano-SiO₂ possesses high pozzolanic activity. A large amount of calcium hydroxide (CH) is generated during the cement hydration process, and Nano-SiO₂ can undergo a secondary reaction with the calcium hydroxide (CH) in the cement hydration products to form additional calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H).

(4) Microstructure Optimization

Nano-SiO₂ can not only fill the tiny pores in cement paste to effectively reduce porosity, but also optimize the structure of C-S-H gel. It promotes the formation of a denser network structure of C-S-H gel, enhancing the activity and stability of hydration products. This optimization enables C-S-H gel to fill pores more effectively and strengthen the internal structure of cement-based materials. The pozzolanic reaction of Nano-SiO₂ further promotes cement hydration, generates more hydration products, fills the internal pores of the material, and improves the material's compactness. Meanwhile, the addition of Nano-SiO₂ can also improve the pore structure of cement-based materials, reduce the number of large pores, optimize pore distribution, and make the material's microstructure more uniform and dense. This optimized microstructure not only enhances the material's mechanical properties but also improves its durability, allowing the material to maintain stable performance during long-term service.

5. Conclusion

(1) The results of the crack self-healing experiment show that both the self-healing sealing materials before and after modification exhibit good crack repair ability. Among them, the material with the optimized ratio can heal cracks of approximately 0.7 mm in width at 5 days (5d). The amount of crack self-healing products generated is sufficient to meet the needs of crack repair, and it still has good crack self-healing potential.

(2) Combined with experimental methods such as Scanning Electron Microscopy-Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), the microstructure and phase composition of hydration products of self-healing sealing materials before and after modification were analyzed. The results show that the hydration products of the control group present a porous structure with high

porosity and a relatively loose overall texture; in contrast, under the modification of nano-silicon dioxide (nano-SiO₂), the microstructure of the materials in the optimized group becomes denser, the porosity decreases, and the contents of calcium (Ca) and silicon (Si) elements increase significantly. There are relatively large amounts of unhydrated tricalcium silicate (C₃S), dicalcium silicate (C₂S), and some sodium-containing (Na-containing) minerals in the control group, while the content of unhydrated components in the optimized group is significantly reduced, the hydration reaction is more sufficient, which accelerates the hydration process, promotes the formation of new hydration products such as afwillite (Ca₅Si₂O₇(CO₃)₂) and sillimanite (Al₂SiO₅), and leads to the generation of more calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel.

(3) The mechanical properties of four modified self-healing sealing materials were comparatively analyzed via uniaxial compressive strength tests. The experimental results show that the compressive strength of the material with the final optimized ratio reaches 8.43 MPa after hardening, which is approximately three times that of the control group, significantly enhancing the mechanical properties of the sealing material. Based on the experimental data, an in-depth investigation was conducted on the mechanism by which admixtures affect the mechanical properties of self-healing sealing materials. The study indicates that the addition of self-healing agents delays the hydration process of Portland cement, leading to a decrease in the mechanical properties of the sealing material. Crack self-healing mainly relies on the secondary hydration and carbonation of cement, and secondary hydration requires the participation of unhydrated cement; therefore, self-healing sealing materials contain a relatively large amount of unhydrated cement. At the same time, their high porosity easily causes excessive carbonation, thereby reducing mechanical properties. However, nano-silicon dioxide (nano-SiO₂), by virtue of its unique nanoscale effect, high specific surface area, and chemical activity, significantly improves the microstructure and mechanical properties of the cement system through mechanisms such as filling effect, accelerating hydration reaction, pozzolanic effect, and microstructure optimization.

(4) In conclusion, this study optimized the ratio of self-healing sealing materials and introduced nano-silicon dioxide (nano-SiO₂) for modification, enabling the material to not only possess excellent crack self-healing ability but also significantly improve its mechanical properties. It thus exhibits great application potential in enhancing the gas extraction effect of coal mine boreholes. To a certain extent, this material can effectively solve the problems of primary sealing failure and difficult secondary sealing construction caused by the occurrence of regenerated cracks in the sealing section after grouting sealing, and meet the requirements for long-term and efficient gas extraction from extraction boreholes.

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